

Whole-genome sequencing of *Bacillus velezensis* Kn15, a strain with an inhibitory behavior against *Rhizoctonia solani*

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Abstract

Bacillus velezensis Kn15 is a gram-positive, endospore-forming bacterium that enhances plant growth and suppresses soil-borne plant pathogens including *Rhizoctonia solani* by producing secondary metabolites. The genome analysis of *B. velezensis* Kn15 reveals that it can serve as a potential candidate for developing new biocontrol agents.

Introduction

Bacillus species are considered typical Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR) producing a vast array of bioactive molecules such as bacillomycin D (Tabbene et al, 2011) and protease enzyme (Gharbi et al, 2018). *Bacillus* genus have been used to control a variety of soil-borne diseases (Marzouk et al, 2021). Specifically, *B.velezensis* has received considerable attention due to its high genetic capacity to produce lipopeptides (Meena et al, 2018, Nam et al, 2021). Furthermore, *B. velezensis* has demonstrated the potential to produce volatile organic compounds such as benzothiazole and 2,4-dimethyl-6-tert-butylphenol with a potential antifungal activity against vascular wilt pathogens (Li et al, 2020) and diacetyl with an antifungal behavior against *Botrytis cinerea* (Calvo et al., 2020). The *B. velezensis* Kn15 produce antifungal soluble compounds including surfactins (92%) and fengycins (8%) with an efficient antifungal activity at 20 µg /µl (unpublished data). This bacterial strain was selected as a potential biological control agent and plant growth stimulator. The whole-genome sequencing (WGS) is a promising method to identify key genes involved in plant growth promotion and antifungal properties in beneficial bacteria.

Material and methods

Bacillus velezensis Kln15 is a bio-control strain isolated from *Solanum tuberosum* leaves following the procedure described by Kalai-Grami et al. (2014). Leaves were washed with tap water and small fragments were divided from the central part of the plant into small fragments. These fragments were surface-sterilized with 70 % ethanol for 2 min, followed by 3.5 % sodium hypochlorite for 10 min and finally washed three times with sterile distilled water. Then placed on LB agar plates and incubated at 28 °C for 48 h. Bacterial isolates were purified and stored at –20 °C in 25% glycerol.

The genomic DNA of Kln15 was sequenced at MicrobesNG using Illumina HiSeq technology. Reads were filtered using Trimmomatic and the filtered reads were assembled into one contig using SPAdes software. The complete genome sequence of Kln15 was annotated using the Prokka at NCBI and taxonomic identification of the genomes sequences was performed by Kraken. The DNA extraction, the Illumina genome sequencing and assembly were conducted by MicrobesNG (The BioHub, Birmingham, UK) according to their protocols <https://microbesng.com/>.

Results

The complete genome sequence assembly of *B. velezensis* Kln15 has been deposited in the NCBI GenBank (Accession no. GCA_020685215.1). The results showed that the genome comprised 3,914,745 bp with the average length of coding genes 161.6 bp, with 46.46% GC content, 83 types of tRNA and 1 cluster of tmRNA, the whole genome was predicted to contain 3688CDSs (protein coding genes).

Statement on continuing work

The datasets are being shared prior to formal publication and should be considered preliminary. We encourage and welcome feedback from the community. Please get in touch with Dr. Naceur DJEBALI for more information.

Acknowledgements

The sequencing of the bacterial strains was supported by the GetGenome initiative of The Sainsbury Laboratory, Norwich, UK, with support from the Gatsby Charitable Foundation and the Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBBSRC).

Table1: Summary statistics for *Bacillus velezensis* genome

Bacterial species	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>
Strain	Kn115
Genome size (bp)	3914745
% GC	46.46%
Number of contigs (>=1000 bp)	32
Largest contig (bp)	830221
Mean coverage (X)	161643
Number of reads	1320090
N50 (bp)	528012
protein-coding gene	3688
tRNA number	83
tmRNA number	1
SRA accession no.	SRR16156310
Assembly accession no.	GCA_020685215.1

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